

DEVELOPMENT OF NON-DESTRUCTIVE DIAGNOSTICS IN BIOTECHNOLOGY USING DIGITAL HOLOGRAPHIC INTERFEROMETRY

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In recent years, the development of the microelectronics elemental base has made the development of non-destructive diagnostics and controls at all technological stages increasingly relevant: from controlling raw materials, semi-finished products, and finished products to analyzing the causes of failures occurring during testing and operation. Among the indispensable methods for local diagnostics are various microprobe techniques, with electron and optical probe methods being the most acceptable and universal.

In comparison with electron probe methods, optical diagnostics in the infrared range allows visualizing volumetric electrically neutral defects such as oxygen and metallic precipitates, packaging defects, dislocations, slip lines, and voids in silicon, gallium arsenide, germanium plates, and products based on them, as well as visualizing various microfields existing in them. The significant penetration depth of IR radiation into semiconductor materials, combined with the registration of signals-responses of various physical nature, allows implementing comprehensive diagnostics of microelectronic products and materials using computer and hardware tomography. Thus, for visualizing and analyzing the structure of microelectronic products, the task of creating multifunctional diagnostic equipment and technology, considering the physical features of contrast formation of images of electro-neutral defects and elements in semiconductor crystals, becomes more important.

In digital holographic interferometry (DHI), digital fields obtained from real fields using digital holography (DH) methods are “interfered” (Jueptner and Schnars, 2004). These methods are based on the Huygens-Fresnel principles, the mathematical apparatus of the Fourier transform, numerical phase development algorithms, and digital image processing algorithms (Wieslter et al., 2007). Unlike conventional interferometry, in which two or more coherent phase fields are needed to obtain a phase interferogram, in DGI it is possible to obtain by calculation the interference field of phase fields that are incoherent with each other (for example, fields that existed at different times and really could not interfere with each other). As a result of digital “interference” of such fields, a virtual interferogram is obtained. A necessary condition for the implementation of single-wave digital digital hysteresis is the smallness of the difference in optical paths between adjacent pixels compared to half the radiation wavelength ($\Delta \leq \lambda/2$). If this condition is violated during the process of restoration (unfolding) of the phase field, an uncertainty arises equal in modulus to 2π . The condition $\Delta \leq \lambda/2$ places a strict limitation on the range of single-wave measurements at the Central Geophysical Institute due to the natural spatial resolution of modern radiation detectors.

One way to eliminate this uncertainty is to use long-wave infrared radiation. However, the practical implementation of this method is limited due to the long-wave sensitivity threshold of radiation receivers. Another method is to use two visible waves of different frequencies

(Schwider et al., 1983; Cheng and Wyant, 1984). In two-color DGI, two data sets are used, obtained at different wavelengths λ_1 and λ_2 . The phase field is restored at the equivalent wavelength $\Lambda_{12} = \lambda_1 \lambda_2 / |\lambda_1 - \lambda_2|$, longer than the wavelengths of the actual visible radiation used. Thus, the use of two-color TsGI significantly softens the requirements for the spatial resolution of radiation detectors, removes uncertainty in the process of reconstructing the phase field, and increases sensitivity. However, this increases noise due to the amplification effect. To find an acceptable compromise, various combinations of virtual and real wavelengths Λ_{12} , λ_1 , λ_2 are used in the form of reference and object waves when reconstructing the phase interferogram. Thus, the technologies developed to date for obtaining information about the interference of multi-colored fields are aimed at solving the problem of 2π uncertainty inherent in all measuring interference methods that use the radiation wavelength as a real measurement measure.

In this work, methods of digital two-exposure interferometry are used - obtaining a difference phase surface that carries information about changes in the object under study during the time between exposures. In this case, holograms of the compared phase fronts were recorded at different wavelengths in pulses of different durations. In our studies of virtual interferograms, we used interferometers assembled according to the Mach-Zehnder and Michelson schemes. Primary digital holograms were recorded in laser radiation with wavelengths of 1.064 μm , 1.054 μm , 0.532 μm , 0.357 μm , in pulses with a duration of 30 ns, 50 ps, 200 fs and in continuous He-Ne laser radiation using a digital camera type TM-1020-15CL with pixel dimensions of 9 x 9 microns.

The photographic objects used were: a plate made of a nonlinear optical crystal LiNbO₃ and a plate made of a photorefractive crystal LiNbO₃:Fe (0.01%). Using recorded multi-colored holograms using the method of two-exposure digital interferometry (Redkorechev, 2009), digital interferograms of various stages of relaxation of phase inhomogeneity recorded in the volume of a photorefractive LiNbO₃:Fe crystal, as well as a nonlinear optical LiNbO₃ crystal, were obtained. Based on the obtained interferograms, phase fronts were reconstructed, carrying quantitative information about the samples under study. A comparison was made of the information obtained - the magnitude of the angle of inclination, the change in the refractive index, the amplitude and length of surface acoustic waves, in various combinations of multi-colored primary phase fronts.

Figure 1 shows a diagram of recording phase holograms. Radiation from a neodymium laser ($\lambda_1=1.06 \mu\text{m}$) with a duration of 30 ns and 50 ps using a mirror (1) was directed into nonlinear optical crystals (2,3), in which the generation of the second and third harmonics of laser radiation with wavelengths $\lambda_2=0.532 \mu\text{m}$ and $\lambda_3=0.357 \mu\text{m}$

Fig. 1. Scheme for recording phase holograms. 1-spectacle. 2,3 - nonlinear frequency multiplication crystals. 4-light filters. 5,7-lens.6-dimensional filter. 8- optical wedge. 10 – mirror. 11 - test sample. 12-CCD camera.

Isolation of radiation at a certain wavelength and change in radiation intensity were carried out using light filters (4). The radiation from He-Ne and femtosecond lasers was not frequency converted. Spatial filtering of radiation was carried out by a spatial filter formed by lenses (5,7) and a diaphragm (6). At the output of the spatial filter, the phase front of the radiation was close to flat. Then the radiation was directed into an interferometer formed by an optical wedge (8) and mirrors (9,10). The sample (11) was located in one of the arms of the interferometer. The holograms were recorded using a CCD camera (12) connected to a personal computer. Based on the processing of the resulting holograms, interferograms were constructed.

The phase inhomogeneity in a photorefractive crystal that occurs in a laser field is determined by the laser radiation intensity $I(t)$, exposure time τ , photorefractive sensitivity of the material K and absorption coefficient α . Figure 2 shows calculated images of phase inhomogeneity in a photorefractive $\text{LiNbO}_3:\text{Fe}$ crystal at different exposure times, corresponding to the interference pattern in digital format. The spatial distribution of laser radiation intensity was assumed to be Gaussian. The exposure time for the image shown in Fig. 2, b, was 3.5 times higher than the exposure time for the image shown in Fig. 2, a. The figure shows that with increasing exposure time, the image of phase inhomogeneity becomes more complex, and an increase in interference fringes appears

a

б

Fig.2. Calculation of the photorefractive structure in a LiNbO₃:Fe crystal.

Figure 3 shows an enlarged image of the volumetric phase inhomogeneity induced in the waist of a focused laser beam, as well as a three-dimensional reconstruction of the phase inhomogeneity recorded in LiNbO₃:Fe by radiation with a wavelength of 532 nm. This image was obtained in the field of nanosecond laser pulses. The polarization of the laser radiation was directed parallel to the main optical axis of the crystal. When the polarization was rotated by 90°, the picture did not change. From the analysis of the recorded phase inhomogeneity shown in this figure, it follows that its appearance qualitatively coincides with the calculated phase distribution (Fig. 2). Some discrepancy may be due to the difference between the laser beam and the Gaussian one. In this case, photorefractive inhomogeneity played the main role.

Fig.3. Interferogram and phase reconstruction of a photorefractive structure

In the field of picosecond laser radiation, the resulting phase inhomogeneity is due to the influence of Kerr nonlinearity. Kerr nonlinearities (and hence the nonlinear addition to the refractive index) are a tensor quantity that relates the third-order polarization components and the corresponding components of the electromagnetic field strength. In the nonlinear optical crystal LiNbO₃, in the absence of losses, Kerr nonlinearities are generally determined by 4 components (Kulagin, 2006). The magnitudes of Kerr nonlinearities depend on the angle of radiation propagation relative to the main optical axis. To calculate the values of Kerr nonlinearities in this case, a semi-empirical model was used. This model is based on taking into account the contribution of one transition in a discrete spectrum.

In this approximation, Kerr nonlinearity is expressed as a function of the refractive index and its second derivative with respect to wavelength. The expression also includes the oscillator density N , which was defined as the average density of atoms in the crystal. Figure 4 shows a simulation of the calculated dependences of the intensity-induced phase shift on spatial coordinates at an angle of radiation propagation to the main axis of the crystal equal to 72° at a wavelength $\lambda = 532$ nm. The initial distribution of laser radiation intensity was assumed to be Gaussian. The following relationship between the nonlinearity components was used in the

calculations: $\chi_{12} : \chi_{14} : \chi_{23} : \chi_{33} = 1 : 0.1 : 0.2 : 6$. Note that the components χ_{14} and χ_{23} made only a small contribution. From the presented figures it is clear that the induced nonlinearity has the form of an ellipse, which, as it approaches the beam axis, turns into a dumbbell-shaped structure elongated along the z axis of the crystal

Fig. 4. Calculated dependence of the phase difference shift in a crystal with 3m symmetry, caused by a change in the refractive index depending on the laser radiation intensity

Figure 5a shows fragments of the central part of the interferogram obtained by passing laser radiation with a wavelength of $1.06 \mu\text{m}$ through an X-cut of a LiNbO_3 crystal 0.2 cm thick at two different radiation intensities. The polarization direction of the radiation coincided with the Y axis. The radiation power density was 10 ГBT/cm^2 .

In accordance with Fig. 2, the difference in the phase of the central part, expressed in units of radiation wavelength, was $0.085 \mu\text{m}$. The calculation showed that the value of the nonlinear part of the refractive index γ was $1.8 \times 10^{-19} \text{ m}^2/\text{W}$. For a given crystal orientation, the nonlinear susceptibility of a class 3m crystal is completely determined by the tensor component χ_{12} , and thus it is possible to determine the nonlinearity tensor components.

Note that for the X-cut of the crystal, the nonlinear change in the refractive index can be due to the process of reverse pumping of the second harmonic energy into the main radiation of the laser radiation. Using the known values of second-order nonlinearity and refractive indices, a correction was determined and the direct value of the nonlinear refractive index due to Kerr nonlinearity was determined, which was $1.12 \times 10^{-19} \text{ m}^2/\text{W}$.

*Fig.5 Fragments of the central part of the interferograms recorded at a wavelength of 1.064 (a)
and 0.532 μm (b)*

Similar measurements of induced optical nonlinearities were carried out at other wavelengths and at different crystal orientations relative to the polarization of laser radiation. Figure 5b shows a fragment of the central part of the interferogram obtained using radiation at the second harmonic wavelength of an Nd:YAG laser. The magnitude of the nonlinearity was ~ 1.4 times higher than the nonlinearity at the fundamental frequency.

The analysis showed the promise of using two-exposure digital holographic interferometry for direct dynamic measurement of phase inhomogeneities arising in a strong laser field and, consequently, measurement of the nonlinear refractive index, photoreactive sensitivity coefficient of the material, and Kerr nonlinear susceptibility.

Thus, the studies have shown the possibility of using digital holographic interferograms obtained using laser radiation at different wavelengths and different durations at different times to reconstruct dynamic phase changes that occur in samples. The most promising practical application of multicolor CGI is in measuring nanometer displacements (nanotechnology, digital microscopy) due to the possibility of using tunable laser radiation sources in the femtosecond range and performing measurements with high time resolution or using cheap laser diodes in spectral ranges available for digital cameras.

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